

Experiment Report

“Impact Test Report of Fast Curing Carbon Composite”

Monem Moktadir*, Asif Istiak*, Hui Yun Hwang

Mechanical Design and System Engineering, Andong National University

According to ASTM 7136 dimension (150mm x 100mm), piecewise integrated composite plates were fabricated. It is a fast-curing composite requiring 5minutes at 150°C, 3MPa pressure while fabrication.

The stacking patterns of the fabricated composites are depicted in Fig. 1 where (a) denotes accordingly T1(70), T1(50), T1(30) and T1(10) composite. And 1(b) denotes T2(30), T2(20) and T2(10) as so, the types of (c) figure can be described as T2(30), T3(20), T3(10). The white grids denote the ply, and the green lines are the indication of ply cut.

Fig 1: Stacking pattern, Type 1 (a), Type 2 (b) and Type 3 (c)

Moreover, 2 sets of specimens were fabricated according to this dimension with no cut and a cut in the middle plane through which are called Reference no cut and Reference_75.

Report: This section is divided into 4 sections for 4 types of patterns. Every section will dictate its own impact characteristics with the description of failure type, Force vs time graph with presentation of pictures. At the end of these sections the overall generalized comment on failure mode and comparison of forces will be discussed. The approximate lengths are measured by ImageJ software.

Failure Mode: Reference_no_cut

Condition	Ref_no_cut_Sample 1		Ref_no_cut_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back	Front	Back
Indentation	Partially		Center lowered (No Puncture)	
Ply Layer Separation	No		Only one quarter of backside	
Separation	No		One Transverse Side	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Both sides (30mm)	Longitudinal (Front)	Left(40mm), right (20mm curved path)
	Transverse (Front)	Both sides (10mm)	Transverse (Front)	Separated(upper), crack line(downside)
	Longitudinal (Back)	Both sides (30mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Left(60mm), Right(40mm)
	Transverse (Back)	Both sides (35mm)	Transverse (Back)	Separated(upper), crack line (downside)
	Stopped on stack line	N/A	Stopped on stack line	N/A
	Go through over stack line	N/A	Go through over stack line	N/A
	Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	At the end of crack (5mm, both sides)	Longitudinal (Front)
Transverse (Front)		Normal to crack line of upper side(18mm)	Transverse (Front)	upper side
Longitudinal (Back)		Along the crack lines	Longitudinal (Back)	Along the crack lines
Transverse (Back)		Upper side; along crack line	Transverse (Back)	Severe on upper side
Stopped on stack line		N/A	Stopped on stack line	N/A
Go through over stack line		N/A	Go through over stack line	N/A

Failure Mode: Reference_75

Condition	Ref_75_Sample 1		Ref_75_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back	Front	Back
Indentation	Center lowered (No Puncture)		Punctured with a round shape	
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides		Front side of punctured area and only one quarter of backside	
Separation	Totally along central Transverse line		Totally along central Transverse line	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Both sides (30mm)	Longitudinal (Front)	No
	Transverse (Front)	Separated	Transverse (Front)	Separated
	Longitudinal (Back)	Both sides (50mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Left(35mm)
	Transverse (Back)	Both sides (35mm)	Transverse (Back)	Separated
	Stopped on stack line	Total separation	Stopped on stack line	Total separation
	Go through over stack line	Total separation	Go through over stack line	Total separation
Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	Both sides (30mm) parallel to the crack line	Longitudinal (Front)	At the end of crack (25mm, both sides)
	Transverse (Front)	Total separation	Transverse (Front)	Total separation
	Longitudinal (Back)	Both sides (40mm) parallel to the crack line	Longitudinal (Back)	Both sides (30mm) parallel to the crack line lines
	Transverse (Back)	Total separation	Transverse (Back)	Sev Total separation
	Stopped on stack line	Total separation	Stopped on stack line	Total separation
	Go through over stack line	Total separation	Go through over stack line	Total separation

Failure Mode: T1

Condition	T1(70)_Sample 1		T1(70)_Sample 2		
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back	Front	Back	
Indentation	Center lowered (No Puncture)		Center lowered (No Puncture)		
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides		Both sides		
Separation	No		No		
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Both sides (30mm)	Longitudinal (Front)	Both sides (35mm)	
	Transverse (Front)	Upper side Separated, crack line on lower side	Transverse (Front)	No	
	Longitudinal (Back)	Both sides (35mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Both sides (35mm)	
	Transverse (Back)	Upper side Separated, crack line on lower side	Transverse (Back)	Both sides (20mm)	
	Stopped on stack line	Before 5mm (front) On the line (back)	Stopped on stack line	On the line (both sides)	
	Go through over stack line	No	Go through over stack line	No	
	Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	No	Longitudinal (Front)	On the crack line
		Transverse (Front)	On the stack line	Transverse (Front)	Crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line	Longitudinal (Back)	Crack line	
	Transverse (Back)	No	Transverse (Back)	Upper side has noticeable breakage	
	Stopped on stack line	Yes	Stopped on stack line	yes	
	Go through over stack line	5mm (both side)	Go through over stack line	Negligible	

Condition	T1(50)_Sample 1		T1(50)_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back	Front	Back
Indentation	One quarter punctured		Center lowered (No Puncture)	
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides		Back side	
Separation	Upper side		No	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Both sides (25mm)	Longitudinal (Front)	Both sides (25mm)
	Transverse (Front)	Upper side Separated, crack line on lower side	Transverse (Front)	Crack line on both sides
	Longitudinal (Back)	Both sides (35mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Both sides (35mm)
	Transverse (Back)	Upper side Separated, crack line on lower side	Transverse (Back)	Both sides (30mm)
	Stopped on stack line	yes	Stopped on stack line	Yes
	Go through over stack line	No(front), 10mm(back)	Go through over stack line	No(front), 10mm(back)
	Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	On the crack line	Longitudinal (Front)
Transverse (Front)		On the stack line	Transverse (Front)	Crack line
Longitudinal (Back)		On the crack line	Longitudinal (Back)	Crack line
Transverse (Back)		On the crack line and punctured area	Transverse (Back)	Minor
Stopped on stack line		Yes	Stopped on stack line	yes
Go through over stack line		Negligible	Go through over stack line	Negligible

Condition	T1(30)_Sample 1			T1(30)_Sample 2		
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back		Front	Back	
Indentation	Half circled punctured			Half circled punctured		
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides			Both sides		
Separation	No			No		
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	No (Punctured area is 30mm)		Longitudinal (Front)	No (Punctured area is 30mm)	
	Transverse (Front)	Punctured area		Transverse (Front)	No	
	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (20mm) and right (50mm)		Longitudinal (Back)	Left (15mm) and right (40mm)	
	Transverse (Back)	Both sides (30mm)		Transverse (Back)	Both sides (30mm)	
	Stopped on stack line	Yes(front) but propagated 35mm on one side(back)		Stopped on stack line	Yes, but propagated more on one side of back	
	Go through over stack line	No(front), 35mm on one side(back)		Go through over stack line	No(front), 25mm on one side(back)	
	Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	Punctured boundary		Longitudinal (Front)	Punctured boundary
Transverse (Front)		Punctured boundary		Transverse (Front)	Punctured boundary	
Longitudinal (Back)		On the crack line		Longitudinal (Back)	Punctured boundary	
Transverse (Back)		On the crack line and punctured area		Transverse (Back)	Punctured boundary	
Stopped on stack line		Yes, but propagated 35mm on one side(back)		Stopped on stack line	Yes, but propagated 25mm on one side(back)	
Go through over stack line		25mm on one side(back)		Go through over stack line	25mm on one side(back)	

Condition	T1(10)_Sample 1		T1(10)_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back	Front	Back
Indentation	Punctured		Punctured	
Ply Layer Separation	Back sides		Both sides	
Separation	No		Totally separated	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	No (Punctured area is 20mm)	Longitudinal (Front)	No (Punctured area is 20mm)
	Transverse (Front)	Between two stacking line	Transverse (Front)	Totally separated
	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (50mm) and right (10mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (50mm) and right (20mm)
	Transverse (Back)	Both sides (45mm)	Transverse (Back)	Totally separated
	Stopped on stack line	Yes(front) but propagated 35mm on one side(back)	Stopped on stack line	Yes, but propagated 35mm one side of back
	Go through over stack line	No(front), 35mm on one side(back)	Go through over stack line	No(front), 35mm on one side(back)
Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	Punctured boundary	Longitudinal (Front)	Punctured boundary
	Transverse (Front)	Punctured boundary and between two stacking line	Transverse (Front)	Totally separated
	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line
	Transverse (Back)	On the crack line and punctured area	Transverse (Back)	Totally separated
	Stopped on stack line	Yes, but propagated 35mm on one side(back)	Stopped on stack line	Yes, but propagated 35mm on one side(back)
	Go through over stack line	35mm on one side(back)	Go through over stack line	35mm on one side(back)

Summary: The puncture was notably seen if the stacking cut line is close to central Transverse line. Moreover, Since, this type has no cut at the central Transverse line the total separation on the Transverse area was barely seen or find fully separation if the is minor deviation in fabrication method like T1(10)_sample 2. The crack line along longitudinal front side usually stops to the stacking cut line. For the distant stacking pattern, we found some cracks on both sides (front and back) over the stacking line. But with the decrease of the distance between zigzag stack line, this tendency has been reduced. One more feature that have been found in this type is, the layer separation detection on the back side of impact point that induces fiber breakage crossing the stacking line on one side. In brief, narrow zigzag pattern inclines to be punctured without transferring the crack and on the other side, broad zigzag patterned specimens initiate huge cracks as well as transfers the crack and fiber breakage over the stacking line though in both case, back side has fiber breakage.

Failure Mode: T2

Condition	T2(10)_Sample 1		T1(10)_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back	Front	Back
Indentation	Punctured		Punctured (half circled)	
Ply Layer Separation	Punctured area		Both sides	
Separation	No		Totally separated	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	No (Punctured area is 20mm)	Longitudinal (Front)	Punctured area up to stacking line; Left side has 25mm crack
	Transverse (Front)	No	Transverse (Front)	Upper part separated; lower part has crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	Between last stacking lines	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (50mm) and right (20mm)
	Transverse (Back)	No	Transverse (Back)	Upper part separated; lower part has crack line
	Stopped on stack line	Yes	Stopped on stack line	Yes but propagated 30mm one side of back
	Go through over stack line	No	Go through over stack line	No(front), 30mm on one side(back)

Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	Punctured area	Longitudinal (Front)	Punctured area
	Transverse (Front)	Punctured area	Transverse (Front)	Along the crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	Between last stacking lines	Longitudinal (Back)	Between last stacking lines and on the crack line
	Transverse (Back)	Between last stacking lines	Transverse (Back)	Along the crack line
	Stopped on stack line	Yes	Stopped on stack line	Yes, but propagated 30mm on one side(back)
	Go through over stack line	No	Go through over stack line	30mm on one side(back) and on that side a normal 30mm breakage line can be seen

Condition	T2(20)_Sample 1		T2(20)_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back	Front	Back
Indentation	Lowered central part		Lowered central part	
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides		No	
Separation	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line		Upper side separated and lower side has crack line	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Left(25mm) and right(20mm)	Longitudinal (Front)	Both sides (20 mm)
	Transverse (Front)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line	Transverse (Front)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (50mm) and right (40mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (50mm) and right (20mm)
	Transverse (Back)	Upper side separated	Transverse (Back)	Upper side separated and lower

		and lower side has crack line			side has crack lines(40mm)
	Stopped on stack line	Yes (between 1 st and second stacking line)		Stopped on stack line	Yes (on the last stack line)
	Go through over stack line	No		Go through over stack line	No
Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	On the cracking line		Longitudinal (Front)	On the crack line
	Transverse (Front)	On the cracking line		Transverse (Front)	On the crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line		Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line
	Transverse (Back)	On the cracking line		Transverse (Back)	On the crack line
	Stopped on stack line	Yes, but breakage found (50mm normal of a crack line found)		Stopped on stack line	Yes, but breakage found (50mm normal of a crack line found)
	Go through over stack line	No		Go through over stack line	No

Condition	T2(30)_Sample 1		T2(30)_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front	Back	Front	Back
Indentation	Lowered central part		Lowered central part	
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides		Both sides	
Separation	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line		Upper side separated and lower side has crack line	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Upto stack line	Longitudinal (Front)	Up to stack line
	Transverse (Front)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line	Transverse (Front)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (50mm) and right (40mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (50mm) and right (20mm)
	Transverse (Back)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line	Transverse (Back)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack lines(40mm)
	Stopped on stack line	Between stack lines	Stopped on stack line	Between stack lines
	Go through over stack line	No	Go through over stack line	No

Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	On the cracking line	Longitudinal (Front)	On the crack line
	Transverse (Front)	On the cracking line	Transverse (Front)	On the crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line
	Transverse (Back)	On the cracking line	Transverse (Back)	On the crack line
	Stopped on stack line	Between stack lines	Stopped on stack line	Between stack lines
	Go through over stack line	No	Go through over stack line	No

Summary: This T2 pattern also showed similar behavior for puncturing. The more parochial the stack lines to the center, the more obvious puncture has been found. With the increase of the stacking line the indentation is eradicating leaving lower centered area after impact. However, this area generally stops on the stacking lines. There are some deviations of stopping the longitudinal line propagation; We found the stoppage between the stacking cut line also. Since, there were cut in the central Transverse line, the specimens were found to be separated partially to this line in every case. Fiber breakage was found more noticeably in the perpendicular path of the crack line. Layer separation on the back side has been lessened than the T1 pattern.

Failure Mode: T3

Condition	T3(10)_Sample 1		T3(10)_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front 			
Indentation	Partially Punctured		Punctured (half circled)	
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides		Both sides	
Separation	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line		Totally separated	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Up to stack line	Longitudinal (Front)	Up to stack line
	Transverse (Front)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line	Transverse (Front)	Totally separated
	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (50mm) and right (40mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (30mm) and right (40mm)
	Transverse (Back)	Upper side separated	Transverse (Back)	Totally separated
			Stopped on stack line	Yes(front); No(Back)
		Go through over stack line	No(front); Yes (Back)	

		and lower side has crack line		
	Stopped on stack line	Yes (front); No (Back)		
	Go through over stack line	No (front); Yes (Back)		
Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	On the cracking line and punctured area	Longitudinal (Front)	On the crack line and punctured boundary
	Transverse (Front)	On the cracking line	Transverse (Front)	On the crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line
	Transverse (Back)	On the cracking line	Transverse (Back)	On the crack line
	Stopped on stack line	Between stack lines	Stopped on stack line	Between stack lines
	Go through over stack line	No	Go through over stack line	No

Condition	T3(20)_Sample 1		T3(20)_Sample 2	
Failure Mode Depiction	Front 			
Indentation	Lowered Centered Area		Lowered Centered Area	
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides		Both sides	
Separation	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line		Upper side separated and lower side has crack line	
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Right (up to first stack line), Left (10mm before 1 st stack line)	Longitudinal (Front)	Up to stack line
	Transverse (Front)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line	Transverse (Front)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	Left (45mm) and right (45mm)	Longitudinal (Back)	Up to stack line
			Transverse (Back)	Upper side

	Transverse (Back)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line			separated and lower side has crack line	
	Stopped on stack line	No (Mixed with between line and on the line)		Stopped on stack line	Yes (1 st layer on the front and last line on the back)	
	Go through over stack line	No(front); Yes (Back)		Go through over stack line	No	
Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	On the cracking line and punctured area		Longitudinal (Front)	On the crack line and punctured boundary	
	Transverse (Front)	On the cracking line		Transverse (Front)	On the crack line	
	Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line		Longitudinal (Back)	On the crack line	
	Transverse (Back)	On the cracking line		Transverse (Back)	On the crack line	
	Stopped on stack line	Both on the line and between the lines were found		Stopped on stack line	Yes	
	Go through over stack line	Yes, found perpendicular breakage on the end of crack line		Go through over stack line	Yes, found perpendicular breakage on the end of crack line	

Condition	T3(30)_Sample 1			T3(30)_Sample 2		
Failure Mode Depiction	Front 					
Indentation	Lowered Centered Area			Lowered Centered Area		
Ply Layer Separation	Both sides.			Both sides.		
Separation	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line			Totally Separated		
Crack Propagation from center	Longitudinal (Front)	Up to first stack line		Longitudinal (Front)	Up to First stack line	
	Transverse (Front)	Upper side separated		Transverse (Front)	Totally Separated	

		and lower side has crack line		Longitudinal (Back)	Between stacking line
	Longitudinal (Back)	Between stacking line		Transverse (Back)	Between stacking line (Back)
	Transverse (Back)	Upper side separated and lower side has crack line		Stopped on stack line	No (Mixed with between line and on the line)
	Stopped on stack line	No (Mixed with between line and on the line)		Go through over stack line	No
	Go through over stack line	No(front); Yes (Back)			
Fiber breakage	Longitudinal (Front)	On the cracking line and perpendicular to the end of that line(40mm)		Longitudinal (Front)	On the cracking line and perpendicular to the end of that line(40mm)
	Transverse (Front)	On the cracking line		Transverse (Front)	On the crack line
	Longitudinal (Back)	On the cracking line and perpendicular to the end of that line(40mm)		Longitudinal (Back)	On the cracking line and perpendicular to the end of that line(40mm)
	Transverse (Back)	On the cracking line		Transverse (Back)	On the crack line
	Stopped on stack line	Both on the line and between the lines were found		Stopped on stack line	Both on the line and between the lines were found
	Go through over stack line	Yes, found perpendicular breakage on the end of crack line		Go through over stack line	Yes, found perpendicular breakage on the end of crack line

Summary: T3 pattern follows almost same conditions of the puncture, crack propagation and fiber breakage phenomenon like T1 and T2. But in this case, we found the crack propagation ended on the first stacking line on the front plane but found the end line of the crack between the stacking lines of the same samples. Moreover, the end of the crack lines contains a perpendicular fiber breakage at the end of it.

Comparison of Failure mode:

- a. Puncture phenomenon depends on the absorbance of the sample. The closer the stacking lines, the more we got the obvious puncture. T1(10), T2(10) and T3(10) have clear punctures than others. Ref_75 has sort of puncture sign but for the cut of the center line it could not hold the total energy that resulted total separation.
- b. Ply layer separation was found more distinctly on the back side than front side. It is quite mercurial for close stacking to the center but for distant stacking it seems spread.
- c. Unlike Reference with no cut and type 1 all the patterns showed upper part separation in the Transverse axis. If we compare the same pattern types, the distant stacking are more vulnerable to being separated fully. Moreover, having cut in the center position in a pattern are more likely to be broken on the Transverse axis.
- d. Another interesting aspect that was found, if the crack propagation on the front side ends in a certain distance, generally, on that sample, we got longer crack propagation on the same axis on the back side.
- e. Close stacking sequence to the centerline ensures less crack propagation breaking on the stack line (Transverse axis). On the other hand, distant stacking sequence has more distributed propagation along the longitudinal axis.
- f. Fiber breakage was found on the crack line and punctured area mainly. But perpendicular breakage of fiber was also found at the end of longitudinal crack end on the distant stacking pattern.

Data of Impact Test:

Specimen Type	No.	Force at Peak (N)	Displacement at Peak (mm)	Energy at Peak (J)	Energy at Total (J)	Impact Energy (J)	Specimen Thickness (mm)
Reference_ No Cut	1	2171	4.6	4.28	28.31	60.00	2.12
	2	2122	6.33	6.6	26.51	60.00	2.17
Reference_75	1	1799	19.79	20.89	22.61	60.00	2.17
	2	1818	14.99	15.71	18.35	60.00	2.17
T1-10	1	1761	4.1	3.14	20.91	60.00	2.18
	2	2305	6.03	7.72	20.92	60.00	2.19
T1-30	1	2526	6.37	7.48	27.4	60.00	2.18
	2	2313	6.5	6.86	21.88	60.00	2.19
T1-50	1	2257	14.82	17.37	23.1	60.00	2.16
	2	2154	4.71	4.42	23.25	60.00	2.30
T1-70	1	2044	6.72	7.86	22.21	60.00	2.18
	2	2405	7.67	8.73	21.34	60.00	2.17
T2-10	1	1931	5.2	4.85	15.65	60.00	2.20
	2	2130	6.59	6.48	23.29	60.00	2.15
T2-20	1	1819	3.93	2.89	22.3	60.00	2.14
	2	2279	5.83	7.16	21.1	60.00	2.12
T2-30	1	2054	7.88	7.51	21.87	60.00	2.20
	2	1861	9.23	9.83	22.81	60.00	2.18
T3-10	1	2109	6.56	6.17	22.68	60.00	2.20
	2	1635	5.24	4.20	20.80	60.00	2.18
T3-20	1	1796	15.90	18.02	24.01	60.00	2.19
	2	2058	6.48	6.42	23.35	60.00	2.15
T3-30	1	2328	7.75	8.31	24.59	60.00	2.18
	2	2155	7.02	7.55	25.35	60.00	2.23

Force vs Time Graphs

